

BRIDGING THE GAP: THE ROLE OF KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES, AND PRACTICE IN NURSES' COMPLIANCE WITH STANDARD PRECAUTIONS IN RESOURCE-LIMITED SETTINGS

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Abstract

Background: Standard precautions are fundamental infection prevention measures applicable to all patient care. Nurses play a pivotal role in implementing these precautions, yet compliance rates vary considerably across healthcare settings, particularly in resource-constrained environments where systemic barriers impact adherence.

Objective: To assess compliance levels with standard precautions among nurses at Saidu Teaching Hospital, Swat, and identify factors associated with knowledge, attitudes, and practice.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted from October 2024 to March 2025 involving 137 registered nurses selected through stratified random sampling. Data were collected using a validated, self-administered questionnaire assessing demographic characteristics, compliance with standard precaution protocols, and barriers and facilitators to compliance.

Results: Participants demonstrated good knowledge of standard precautions (mean 24.68 ± 3.91 ; 95% CI: 23.96–25.40) and positive attitudes (mean 27.39 ± 3.57 ; 95% CI: 26.77–28.01), yet exhibited moderate practice adherence (mean 22.47 ± 4.26 ; 95% CI: 21.64–23.30). Formal infection control training was significantly associated with both knowledge ($p < 0.001$) and practice scores ($p = 0.006$). Bachelor's degree nurses demonstrated significantly higher knowledge ($p = 0.022$) and attitudes ($p = 0.045$) compared to diploma holders. Moderate positive correlations were observed among knowledge, attitude, and practice ($r = 0.391-0.462$, $p < 0.01$). **Conclusion:** A significant knowledge–attitude–practice gap exists, reflecting systemic barriers in resource-limited settings. Targeted infection control training and organizational support are critical for improving compliance.

INTRODUCTION

Healthcare-associated infections (HAIs) represent a significant global public health challenge, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where resource constraints compound transmission risks (1). Standard precautions, as defined by the World Health

Organization and the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, constitute the fundamental infection prevention measures applicable to all patient care, regardless of suspected or confirmed infection status. These precautions encompass hand hygiene, personal

protective equipment (PPE) use, safe injection practices, safe handling of contaminated equipment, and environmental cleaning (2).

Nurses, representing the largest proportion of healthcare workers and providing continuous patient care, play a pivotal role in implementing standard precautions. However, compliance rates vary considerably across different healthcare settings, with particularly concerning levels reported in resource-limited environments (3). Previous studies have documented compliance rates in developing countries at approximately 53% (95% CI: 47–59%), significantly lower than the 90% benchmark recommended by international infection control standards (4).

Pakistan's healthcare system faces substantial challenges related to resource scarcity, inadequate infrastructure, high patient-to-nurse ratios, and limited infection prevention training opportunities (5). Saidu Teaching Hospital in Swat district serves as a major tertiary care facility for the Malakand division, providing care to a large, multi-district regional population. The hospital operates under considerable resource constraints, including limited PPE availability, inadequate staffing, and high patient volumes, creating an environment where standard precaution compliance may be compromised (6).

Multiple factors have been identified in the literature as influencing nurses' adherence to standard precautions, including individual characteristics (knowledge, attitudes, experience), organizational factors (availability of resources, administrative support, workload), and systemic issues (training opportunities, supervision, institutional policies) (7). However, the interplay of these factors in resource-scarce settings remains inadequately explored, particularly in the Pakistani context. Understanding the specific factors associated with compliance in resource-limited settings is essential for developing contextually appropriate interventions. This study aims to assess compliance levels with standard precautions among nurses at Saidu Teaching Hospital and identify factors associated with compliance, thereby contributing evidence to inform policy and practice improvements in similar resource-constrained environments.

Methods

Study Design and Setting

This study employed a quantitative cross-sectional design conducted at Saidu Teaching Hospital, Swat, Pakistan, from October 2024 to March 2025.

Study Population and Sampling

The study included 137 registered nurses working at Saidu Teaching Hospital, Swat. Participants were selected using stratified random sampling to ensure representation across all departments. Inclusion criteria specified that nurses must have at least two years of clinical experience and be directly involved in patient care.

Data Collection Instrument

Data were collected using a validated, self-administered questionnaire adapted from previously published studies (8). The instrument was pilot-tested with 20 nurses to ensure clarity and appropriateness. Cronbach's alpha coefficients confirmed acceptable internal consistency across domains: knowledge scale ($\alpha = 0.78$), attitude scale ($\alpha = 0.81$), and practice scale ($\alpha = 0.76$). The instrument consisted of three sections:

Demographic Profile: This section included age, gender, educational qualification, professional experience, and department.

Standard

Precautions Compliance Assessment: An item scale measured compliance with five protocol components: hand hygiene, PPE use, safe injection practices, sharps disposal, and environmental cleaning. Raw scores were converted to a 0–30 scale. Score interpretation was defined a priori as follows: poor adherence (0–15), moderate adherence (16–23), and good adherence (24–30).

Factors Affecting Compliance: A checklist identified barriers and facilitators of compliance, including resource availability, time constraints, workload, training, administrative support, and personal factors.

Data Collection and Analysis

Written informed consent was obtained from all participants after explaining the study's

purpose and emphasizing the voluntary nature of participation. Questionnaires were distributed among nursing staff for data collection. Data were entered into SPSS version 25.0 for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, means, standard deviations) and 95% confidence intervals were computed for demographic variables and compliance scores. Independent samples t-tests and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to compare mean scores between groups. Pearson correlation analysis assessed relationships among variables. Multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to identify independent predictors of practice adherence. Statistical significance was defined as $p < 0.05$.

Results

Study Sample and Demographic Characteristics

A total of 137 nurses from Saidu Teaching Hospital, Swat, participated in this study. The

mean age of participants was 29.8 ± 5.4 years (95% CI: 28.86–30.74), with the majority (29.9%) between 26 and 29 years old. The gender distribution was nearly equal, with 49.6% males and 50.4% females. More than half of the participants (53.3%) were married, and 62.0% held a Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) degree, while 38.0% held a diploma qualification. Regarding work experience, 30.7% had 2–5 years, 26.3% had 6–9 years, 22.6% had 10–13 years, and 20.4% had 14 or more years. Participants represented eight hospital departments, with the highest representation from the Intensive Care Unit (19.0%), Emergency Room (17.5%), and Cardiac Care Unit (16.1%). Notably, 51.8% of participants reported having received previous infection control training, while 48.2% had not.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Participants (N = 137)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)	22–25	28	20.4
	26–29	41	29.9
	30–33	36	26.3
	34 and above	32	23.4
Gender	Male	68	49.6
	Female	69	50.4
Marital Status	Married	73	53.3
	Single	64	46.7
Education	BSN	85	62.0
	Diploma	52	38.0
Experience (years)	2–5	42	30.7
	6–9	36	26.3
	10–13	31	22.6
	14+	28	20.4
Department	Cardiac Care Unit	22	16.1
	Emergency Room	24	17.5
	Intensive Care Unit	26	19.0
	Maternity	15	10.9
	Medical Ward	19	13.9
	Orthopedic	8	5.8
	Pediatrics	9	6.6
	Surgical Ward	14	10.2
Previous IPC Training	Yes	71	51.8
	No	66	48.2

Knowledge, Practice, and Attitude Toward Standard Precautions

The descriptive statistics for knowledge, practice, and attitude scores are presented in Table 2. The mean knowledge score was 24.68 ± 3.91 (95% CI: 23.96–25.40; range: 14–30), indicating that participants possessed good knowledge of standard precautions (score ≥ 24). The mean practice score was 22.47 ± 4.26 (95%

CI: 21.64–23.30; range: 12–30), suggesting moderate adherence to standard infection control protocols in clinical practice (scores 16–23). Notably, participants demonstrated positive attitudes toward infection prevention, with a mean attitude score of 27.39 ± 3.57 (95% CI: 26.77–28.01; range: 17–30), representing good attitude scores (≥ 24).

Table 2. Knowledge, Practice, and Attitude Scores (N = 137)

Variable	Mean \pm SD	95% CI	Minimum	Maximum
Knowledge Score	24.68 ± 3.91	23.96–25.40	14	30
Practice Score	22.47 ± 4.26	21.64–23.30	12	30
Attitude Score	27.39 ± 3.57	26.77–28.01	17	30

Association of Demographic Variables with Knowledge, Practice, and Attitude

Several demographic factors demonstrated significant associations with knowledge and attitude toward standard precautions, as presented in Table 3. Educational qualification showed significant associations with both knowledge and attitude scores. Participants with a BSN degree (mean 25.44 ± 3.52 , 95% CI: 24.53–26.35) demonstrated significantly higher knowledge scores compared to diploma holders (mean 23.35 ± 3.98 , 95% CI: 21.89–24.81; $t = 2.31$, $p = 0.022$). Similarly, BSN nurses showed significantly more positive attitudes (mean 28.05 ± 3.21 , 95% CI: 27.24–28.86) compared to diploma holders (mean 26.33 ± 3.88 , 95% CI: 25.05–27.61; $t = 2.03$, $p = 0.045$).

Work experience was significantly associated with knowledge ($F(3,133) = 3.18$, $p = 0.026$). Analysis revealed that nurses with 10–13 years of experience demonstrated the highest mean knowledge scores (mean 25.87 ± 3.45), followed by those with 14+ years (mean 25.18 ± 3.88), 6–9 years (mean 24.17 ± 4.00), and 2–5 years (mean 23.88 ± 3.97). However, experience did not significantly influence practice ($F(3,133) = 2.54$, $p = 0.059$) or attitude scores ($F(3,133) = 1.29$, $p = 0.281$).

Department of work showed significant associations with knowledge ($F(7,129) = 2.76$, $p = 0.010$) and attitude ($F(7,129) = 2.33$, $p = 0.030$), with the Intensive Care Unit demonstrating the highest mean knowledge and attitude scores. Departmental assignment did not significantly affect practice scores ($F(7,129) = 1.84$, $p = 0.087$).

Gender and marital status demonstrated no significant associations with knowledge ($t = 1.12$, $p = 0.265$ and $t = 0.97$, $p = 0.334$, respectively), practice ($t = 0.84$, $p = 0.404$ and $t = 1.42$, $p = 0.159$, respectively), or attitude scores ($t = 1.36$, $p = 0.177$ and $t = 0.64$, $p = 0.524$, respectively). Notably, previous infection prevention control (IPC) training was significantly associated with both knowledge and practice. Nurses who had received formal training (mean 26.34 ± 2.85 , 95% CI: 25.58–27.10) demonstrated significantly higher knowledge scores ($t = 3.54$, $p < 0.001$) compared to those without prior training (mean 22.68 ± 4.22 , 95% CI: 21.51–23.85). Similarly, trained nurses showed better practice adherence (mean 23.76 ± 3.84 , 95% CI: 22.74–24.78) compared to untrained nurses (mean 21.06 ± 4.41 , 95% CI: 19.78–22.34; $t = 2.78$, $p = 0.006$).

Table 3. Association of Demographic Variables with Knowledge, Practice, and Attitude Scores. * $p < 0.05$ indicates statistical significance.

Variable	Knowledge (Mean \pm SD)	p-value	Practice (Mean \pm SD)	p-value	Attitude (Mean \pm SD)	p-value
Gender	$t = 1.12$	0.265	$t = 0.84$	0.404	$t = 1.36$	0.177

Marital Status	t = 0.97	0.334	t = 1.42	0.159	t = 0.64	0.524
Education (BSN vs. Diploma)	t = 2.31	0.022*	t = 1.15	0.252	t = 2.03	0.045*
Experience	F(3,133) = 3.18	0.026*	F(3,133) = 2.54	0.059	F(3,133) = 1.29	0.281
Department	F(7,129) = 2.76	0.010*	F(7,129) = 1.84	0.087	F(7,129) = 2.33	0.030*
IPC Training (Yes vs. No)	t = 3.54	<0.001*	t = 2.78	0.006*	t = 1.89	0.061

Relationships Among Knowledge, Practice, and Attitude

Pearson correlation analysis examined the relationships among knowledge, practice, and attitude scores, as shown in Table 4. All three variables demonstrated statistically significant positive correlations with one another (p < 0.01). Knowledge and practice were moderately correlated (r = 0.462, 95% CI: 0.309-0.595, p < 0.01), indicating that higher knowledge of standard precautions was associated with improved adherence in clinical practice.

Similarly, knowledge and attitude were significantly correlated (r = 0.391, 95% CI: 0.230-0.535, p < 0.01), suggesting that better understanding of infection control measures was associated with more positive attitudes toward their implementation. Additionally, practice and attitude showed a moderate positive correlation (r = 0.428, 95% CI: 0.268-0.570, p < 0.01), indicating that nurses with more positive attitudes toward standard precautions demonstrated better adherence in clinical practice.

Table 4. Pearson Correlation Matrix Among Knowledge, Practice, and Attitude Scores. **p < 0.01 indicates highly significant correlation.

Variable	Knowledge	Practice	Attitude
Knowledge	1	r = 0.462** (95% CI: 0.309-0.595)	r = 0.391** (95% CI: 0.230-0.535)
Practice	r = 0.462** (95% CI: 0.309-0.595)	1	r = 0.428** (95% CI: 0.268-0.570)
Attitude	r = 0.391** (95% CI: 0.230-0.535)	r = 0.428** (95% CI: 0.268-0.570)	1

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to identify independent predictors of practice adherence (Table 5). The model included education, work experience, department, and IPC training status as independent variables. Results demonstrated that IPC training status remained a significant independent predictor of practice adherence (β = 2.71, 95% CI: 0.89-4.53, p = 0.004), with

trained nurses demonstrating approximately 2.71 points higher practice scores. Educational qualification showed a trend toward significance (β = 1.64, 95% CI: -0.08-3.36, p = 0.061). Work experience and department assignment did not emerge as independent predictors in the multivariable model. The overall model explained 18% of the variance in practice adherence (R² = 0.18).

Table 5. Multiple Linear Regression Model for Practice Adherence. *p < 0.05 indicates statistical significance. Model R² = 0.18.

Predictor	β	95% CI	p-value
IPC Training	2.71	0.89-4.53	0.004*
Education (BSN vs. Diploma)	1.64	-0.08-3.36	0.061
Work Experience	0.31	-0.15-0.77	0.189
Department	0.42	-0.38-1.22	0.296

Discussion

This cross-sectional study examined the knowledge, attitudes, and practice of standard precautions among nurses at Saidu Teaching Hospital in Swat, Pakistan, and investigated factors associated with compliance. The findings reveal a notable discrepancy between nurses' theoretical knowledge and actual clinical practice, with moderate adherence rates despite good awareness and positive attitudes toward infection prevention. Nurses at Saidu Teaching Hospital demonstrated good knowledge of standard precautions (mean score 24.68 ± 3.91 , 95% CI: 23.96–25.40) and positive attitudes toward infection prevention (mean 27.39 ± 3.57 , 95% CI: 26.77–28.01), but exhibited moderate adherence to practice guidelines (mean 22.47 ± 4.26 , 95% CI: 21.64–23.30). This pattern is consistent with global findings from resource-constrained environments, where healthcare workers generally recognize the importance of precautions but encounter challenges in maintaining consistent practice. A recent meta-analysis across low- and middle-income countries reported an overall compliance estimate of approximately 53%, reflecting similar challenges (4). Multiple studies have similarly observed that many nurses demonstrate excellent knowledge yet achieve only moderate compliance scores, underscoring a broader issue in resource-limited healthcare systems where knowledge and attitudes alone are insufficient to ensure consistent adherence (9–11).

The study identified moderate positive correlations among all three variables, indicating that these elements are interrelated, though not perfectly associated. Knowledge and practice showed a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.462$, 95% CI: 0.309–0.595, $p < 0.01$), suggesting that higher knowledge is associated with improved adherence in clinical practice. Knowledge and attitude were also significantly correlated ($r = 0.391$, 95% CI: 0.230–0.535, $p < 0.01$), indicating that better understanding is associated with more positive attitudes. Additionally, practice and attitude showed a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.428$, 95% CI: 0.268–0.570, $p < 0.01$). These findings are consistent with other studies reporting similar

knowledge–practice associations among nurses in comparable contexts. However, despite generally good knowledge and attitudes, actual practice remained only moderate (12, 13), highlighting the complexity of translating awareness into behavior. Resource limitations are well-documented in settings such as Saidu Hospital, where shortages of personal protective equipment and high patient-to-staff ratios have been identified as significant barriers that may limit compliance regardless of individual knowledge or attitudes (14).

Formal infection control training emerged as the most significant factor associated with improved compliance outcomes. Nurses who had received IPC training demonstrated substantially higher knowledge scores (mean 26.34 ± 2.85 vs. 22.68 ± 4.22 ; $p < 0.001$) and better practice adherence (mean 23.76 ± 3.84 vs. 21.06 ± 4.41 ; $p = 0.006$) compared to untrained colleagues. In the multivariable regression model, IPC training remained a significant independent predictor of practice adherence ($\beta = 2.71$, 95% CI: 0.89–4.53, $p = 0.004$). These findings suggest that targeted training interventions may be associated with meaningful improvements in compliance. Previous research similarly highlights training as a modifiable factor, with studies indicating that compliance may improve following systematic educational interventions in standard precautions (15).

Educational qualification was significantly associated with knowledge and attitude. Nurses holding a Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) degree demonstrated higher knowledge scores (mean 25.44 ± 3.52 vs. 23.35 ± 3.98 ; $p = 0.022$) and more positive attitudes (mean 28.05 ± 3.21 vs. 26.33 ± 3.88 ; $p = 0.045$) compared to diploma nurses. In the multivariable model, BSN qualification showed a trend toward independent significance for practice adherence ($\beta = 1.64$, 95% CI: -0.08 –3.36, $p = 0.061$). These patterns suggest that higher-level education may be associated with greater understanding and motivation toward infection prevention practices. Previous studies similarly report that nurses with bachelor's degrees or higher education consistently demonstrate greater knowledge and more positive attitudes

toward infection prevention compared to those with diploma-level education (16–18).

Departmental assignment was significantly associated with knowledge ($p=0.010$) and attitude ($p=0.030$), with the Intensive Care Unit demonstrating higher mean scores. Although cross-sectional data cannot establish causality, these variations may reflect differences in departmental protocols, implementation fidelity, and intensity of infection prevention training programs. Studies from diverse regions consistently report that organizational factors play a critical role in influencing healthcare workers' adherence to infection prevention and control practices. Key organizational determinants include administrative support, workload, staffing levels, and resource availability (19). However, in the multivariable model, departmental assignment did not emerge as an independent predictor of practice adherence, suggesting that observed associations may be mediated by other factors such as training intensity or resource availability specific to those departments.

Work experience was significantly associated with knowledge ($p=0.026$) but did not independently predict practice adherence in the multivariable model. Gender and marital status demonstrated no significant associations with any outcome measure, suggesting that professional factors outweigh personal demographics in shaping infection prevention compliance. These findings emphasize the importance of targeting organizational and professional development interventions rather than individual demographic characteristics to improve adherence to infection prevention protocols.

Limitations

This study was conducted at a single hospital using a cross-sectional design, which limits the ability to establish causal relationships between variables. Compliance was assessed through self-reported questionnaires rather than direct observation, which may result in overestimation of actual adherence. The sample size of 137 nurses was adequate for this setting but findings may not apply to other hospitals in Pakistan or other low- and middle-income countries. The study did not measure actual

infection rates or patient outcomes, so the real-world impact of these compliance levels cannot be fully determined.

Recommendations

Hospitals should implement systematic infection control training programs for all nursing staff and ensure adequate resources including PPE availability and appropriate staff-to-patient ratios. Future research should employ direct observational methods and multi-center studies in diverse healthcare settings.

Conclusion

Nurses at Saidu Teaching Hospital showed good knowledge and positive attitudes toward standard precautions, but their actual compliance in practice was only moderate. This gap between what nurses know and what they do highlights common challenges in resource-limited healthcare settings, where various barriers make it difficult to consistently follow infection control measures. Formal infection control training was the strongest factor linked with better compliance, even after considering education and other demographic variables. These findings suggest that focused, evidence-based interventions especially regular training and adequate resources can help improve adherence to standard precautions. Future research using observational methods and intervention studies is needed to confirm these results and identify effective strategies for improving compliance in resource constrained environments.

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